

Table S2. Accuracy of ultrasonography for the detection of lesions in different localizations and predictions of disease stage, surgical complexity, and residual disease, stratified by presence of ascites detected by ultrasonography.

Parameter	Ascites in ultrasound	Sensitivity %	Specificity %	PPV¹ %	NPV² %	Accuracy
Omentum, gross involvement	Yes	96.9	89.4	89.9	96.7	93.1
	No	100	93.6	85.7	100	95.4
Omentum, small nodules	Yes	17.4	97.2	57.1	84.6	83.1
	No	16.7	96.2	50.0	83.6	81.5
Small bowel mesentery root	Yes	89.1	92.3	97.6	70.6	89.8
	No	100	-	100	-	100
Peritoneum, abdomen	Yes	75.0	67.3	34.6	92.1	68.8
	No	91.1	19.1	70.7	50.0	68.2
Peritoneum, pelvis	Yes	75.0	90.2	33.3	98.2	89.2
	No	80.8	67.5	61.8	84.4	72.7
Liver hilum	Yes	98.0	50.0	87.7	87.5	87.7
	No	100	20.0	93.9	100	93.9
Spleen, parenchymal	Yes	100	-	100	-	100
	No	100	100	100	100	100
Spleen, hilum	Yes	82.5	88.0	91.7	75.9	84.6
	No	96.2	57.1	89.3	80.0	87.9
Diaphragm, right	Yes	60.0	63.0	23.1	89.5	62.5
	No	97.4	52.0	76.0	92.9	79.7
Diaphragm, left	Yes	87.5	16.7	63.6	44.4	60.9
	No	100	30.0	88.7	100	89.2
Frozen pelvis	Yes	95.3	77.3	89.1	89.5	89.2
	No	94.2	75.0	94.2	75.0	90.6
Rectum	Yes	80.7	97.1	96.2	84.6	89.2
	No	82.1	85.2	88.9	76.7	83.3
Stage prediction ³	Yes	91.7	60.0	96.5	37.5	89.2
	No	83.3	83.3	93.0	65.2	83.3
Surgical prediction ⁴ complexity	Yes	82.3	78.6	60.9	91.7	79.7
	No	84.0	64.3	67.7	81.8	73.6
Residual prediction ⁵ disease	Yes	41.2	97.6	87.5	80.4	81.4
	No	41.2	97.2	87.5	77.8	79.2

¹ PPV, positive predictive value; ² NPV, negative predictive value; ³ stage prediction: early or advanced; ⁴ Surgical complexity as defined in publication Aletti D.G. et al. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* **2007**; 197: 676.e671-677, analysed only if open surgery with attempted cytoreduction or full staging (n=113), stratified into two subgroups: low/intermediate and high; ⁵ Residual disease after surgery – prediction based on ultrasonography, without stratification into early or advanced disease, analysed only if open surgery with attempted cytoreduction or full staging (n = 113).